

Preparation of procedure proposal for the Ethics committee

The tables for ANESTHESIA AND ANALGESIA

Francisco E. Olucha-Bordonau

UJI

In the objective of advancing in preparing the procedure proposal to meet all requirements according to ethical and deontological rules in each BC and TC. Centralizing all documents in each experimental WP for procedure validation and ethical approval. Along the first semester, all procedures will need to be approved by local committees/Ministry.

One of the most important aspects to address measures is to avoid animal pain and suffering by providing anesthesia and/or analgesia in specific moments of experimentation

For the PsyCoMed procedures it is recommend the tables for standard operating systems of anesthesia and analgesia provided by McGill University which also includes rodents, amphibians and fish that are the three biological groups that we are going to use in the project

That can be obtained from

<https://www.mcgill.ca/research/research/compliance/animals/animal-research-practices/sop>